

Electrochemical DNA biosensor coupled to LAMP reaction for early diagnostics of cervical precancerous lesions

Ravery Sebuyoya^{a,b}, Ludmila Moranova^a, Nasim Izadi^a, Lukas Moran^{a,c}, Roman Hrstka^a, Milan Anton^d, Martin Bartosik^{a,*}

^a Research Centre for Applied Molecular Oncology, Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute, Zluty kopec 7, 656 53, Brno, Czech Republic

^b National Centre for Biomolecular Research, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kamenice 5, 625 00, Brno, Czech Republic

^c Department of Histology and Embryology, Faculty of Medicine, Masaryk University, 625 00, Brno, Czech Republic

^d Dept. Obstet. Gynecol., Univ. Hosp. Brno, Medical Faculty Masaryk University, Obilni trh 11, 602 00, Brno, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Electrochemistry

HPV

Screen-printed electrode

DNA biosensor

Loop-mediated isothermal amplification

Cervical cancer

ABSTRACT

Electrochemical (EC) biosensors are potentially useful tools for detection of DNA and RNA cancer biomarkers. Gold screen-printed electrodes (AuSPEs) are especially popular due to their easy manufacturing and surface modifications, making them useful candidates in biosensor fabrication. On the other hand, biosensors based on AuSPEs are still not often applied to clinical samples from cancer patients or compared with routine laboratory methods. Therefore, we tried to address these challenges by developing AuSPE-based biosensor for detection of DNA from two highly oncogenic types of human papillomavirus (HPV), HPV16 and HPV18, that cause cervical cancer in women. We coupled loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) of HPV DNA from fifteen clinical samples, with the capture of amplified products at the surface of the AuSPE and with final EC detection in a multielectrode format. We show excellent selectivity of designed primers and probes by comparing HPV-positive and HPV-negative cancer cell lines, and most importantly, very good sensitivity and specificity of the proposed biosensor for detection of clinical samples when compared to the PCR used as a gold standard.

1. Introduction

Nucleic acids, i.e., DNA and RNA, serve an important role as tumor biomarkers that proved to be helpful in early diagnostics, cancer prognosis as well as in predicting therapy outcome (Martens et al., 2009; Mikeska et al., 2012; Pessoa et al., 2020; Wittmann and Jack 2010; Xi et al., 2017). These biomarkers include, for instance, abnormally methylated DNA, circulating tumor DNA, viral nucleic acids, or non-coding RNA molecules, particularly microRNAs (miRNAs) and long non-coding RNAs (lncRNA). Methods of their detection are quite diverse, relying mostly on optical readout (Real-Time PCR with fluorescence detection, gel or capillary electrophoresis, next-generation sequencing, and many others). Despite a great technological progress in recent years, existing methods still face various challenges, such as high cost, complex or long protocols, or requirement of skilled personnel, all of which limit their use, especially in low-resource settings.

To address these challenges, electrochemical (EC) DNA biosensors have shown to be promising alternatives for detection of various cancer

biomarkers based on nucleic acids (Bartosik and Jirakova 2019; Campuzano et al., 2017a, b; Ferapontova 2017; Kilic et al., 2018; Miranda-Castro et al., 2019). They offer interesting features in terms of simple instrumentation and operation, low cost, rapid detection times, flexibility of design and numerous surface modifications, miniaturization that comes hand in hand with a low sample consumption, and the possibility of simultaneous measurements at multiplexed electrode arrays, which is an important prerequisite for their eventual clinical application at the point-of-care (Mincu et al., 2020).

Gold screen-printed electrodes (AuSPEs) are especially popular types of electrodes due to their easy manufacturing and surface modification with self-assembled monolayers (SAMs), comprising thiolated (SH) DNA probes to capture target nucleic acids, as well as various small thiolated molecules that block the surface and thus prevent non-specific adsorptions (Mandler and Kraus-Ophir 2011; Voccia et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2010). Despite a frequent utilization of AuSPEs for detection of DNA/RNA cancer biomarkers (Islam et al., 2017; Nabok et al., 2021), not many studies (a) demonstrate the feasibility of EC biosensors by using human clinical samples, (b) properly validate the biosensor with

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: martin.bartosik@mou.cz (M. Bartosik).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosx.2022.100224>

Received 26 May 2022; Received in revised form 29 July 2022; Accepted 16 August 2022

Available online 23 August 2022

2590-1370/© 2022 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

standard methods of detection, or (c) provide more comprehensive statistics that would indicate potential use in real clinical practice.

Here, we address these challenges by developing a simple EC biosensor for detection of an important class of DNA cancer biomarkers, i.e., DNA from human papillomavirus (HPV). HPV infection is known to be a major etiological factor of cervical cancer in women (Schiffman et al., 2007; Steenbergen et al., 2014), and it also plays a role in the development of other anogenital (Dunne and Park 2013) or even head and neck cancers (Osazuwa-Peters et al., 2017). Although majority of HPV infections are cleared by an immune system, a small part of the persistent high-risk HPV infections may progress to precancerous lesions, and if not diagnosed and treated, may lead to cancer. This transformation is characterized by an increased expression of *E6* and *E7* viral oncogenes (Morris 2005) which are thus most often targeted when diagnosing the infection. Our effort was to detect DNA from the two most frequent oncogenic types, HPV16 and HPV18, accounting for over 70% of all cervical cancers (Sommerova et al., 2019; Steenbergen et al., 2014). Despite the availability of commercial HPV diagnostic kits, many women, especially from low-income countries, still lack an access to a simple and rapid HPV test with sufficient quality.

Previously, we have developed several EC assays for detection of HPV infection (Anton et al., 2020; Bartosik et al. 2016, 2018; Izadi et al., 2021) to distinguish healthy women from those having precancerous lesions, i.e., high-grade intraepithelial lesions (HSILs) that slowly turn into cervical carcinomas if left untreated. The first was a PCR-based EC assay targeting the HPV16 type (Bartosik et al., 2016). In the second assay, we replaced PCR with an isothermal amplification technique called loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP), showing high sensitivity by using constant temperature and short reaction time. In that assay, we targeted both HPV16 and HPV18 types (Anton et al., 2020; Bartosik et al., 2018; Izadi et al., 2021) and were able to detect HPV DNA not only after DNA extraction from cervical cells (Anton et al., 2020; Bartosik et al. 2016, 2018), but also directly from a cell lysate without DNA extraction (Izadi et al., 2021). Nevertheless, all these approaches required magnetic beads for DNA separation and subsequent transfer of the beads to the electrode surface.

In this work, we omitted an application of magnetic beads and determined HPV DNA directly on AuSPE using thiolated DNA capture probes for both HPV types. By using LAMP amplification, we were able to detect picogram amounts of DNA from cervical cancer cells. The designed primers and probes showed good selectivity, easily discriminating HPV-positive and HPV-negative cancer cells. Most importantly, the optimized biosensor was applied to clinical samples to evaluate its performance when discriminating precancerous HSILs from healthy samples. We obtained excellent correlation with PCR as a gold standard, and our biosensor showed very good sensitivity, specificity, and inter-rater reliability (kappa values) with the PCR. We also addressed an issue of cross-reactivity that we observed when LAMP products of different HPV types nonspecifically adsorbed to the AuSPE and gave rise to high background noise. This was suppressed by applying an extra blocking step.

This rapid and simple EC biosensor can thus detect two of the most frequent HPV types directly in clinical precancerous samples.

2. Experimental

2.1. Material and apparatus

We obtained PPP Master Mix for the PCR amplification from Top-Bio (Czech Republic), WarmStart LAMP Kit (DNA & RNA) for the LAMP reaction from New England Biolabs (USA), 6-mercapto-1-hexanol (MCH), hexanedithiol, dithiothreitol (DTT), bovine serum albumin (BSA) and streptavidin–peroxidase polymer (SPP) from Merck (USA), biotin-16-dUTP (bio-dUTP) from Jena Bioscience (Germany), casein blocking buffer (Blocker™ Casein in PBS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (USA), and Enhanced K-Blue® TMB Substrate (3,3',5,5'-

tetramethylbenzidine, TMB) for peroxidase from Neogen (USA). All other chemicals were of analytical grade and solutions were made in deionized water.

Primers for LAMP reaction were designed using PrimerExplorer V.5 software, targeting gene region *E6* in HPV16 and *E7* region in HPV18 genotype. Primers and thiolated DNA capture probes were synthesized by Generi Biotech (Czech Republic). Their sequences and lengths of PCR amplicons are shown in Table S1. Thermocycler T100™ for amplification reactions was from Bio-Rad (USA).

The multipotentiostat/multigalvanostat μ Stat 8000 (Metrohm DropSens, Spain) was connected to an electrochemical array made of eight cells (Metrohm DropSens, DRP-8X220AT), each in a three-electrode configuration comprising gold working and auxiliary electrodes and silver as a pseudoreference electrode.

2.2. Cell lines

Cervical carcinoma cell lines CaSki and SiHa (as HPV16 positive controls) were cultivated in RPMI medium (Merck, USA), cervical carcinoma cell line HeLa (HPV18 positive control), mammary adenocarcinoma cell line MCF-7 and human colorectal adenocarcinoma cell line HT-29 were cultured in DMEM (Merck, USA), and cervical cancer line C4-I (also HPV18 positive control) was cultivated in McCoy's medium (Merck, USA). Media contained 1% L-glutamin (for RPMI), 1% pyruvate (for DMEM) and penicillin-streptomycin (Biosera, France) and 10% FBS (Fetal Bovine Serum from Gibco, USA). All cells were grown at 37 °C under a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂. DNA extraction was performed with DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen, Germany), according to the manufacturer's instructions.

2.3. Clinical samples

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study. The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethical Committee of the University Hospital in Brno. Cervical samples were collected by a gynecologist into homogenization solution (0.4 M ammonium thiocyanate, 0.8 M guanidine thiocyanate, 0.1 M sodium acetate, 5% glycerol, 38% phenol) and stored at –80 °C in Bank of Biological Material at Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute for further use. DNA was isolated by DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen, Germany), according to the manufacturer's instructions. HPV genotyping was performed in a certified clinical laboratory with INNO-LiPA HPV Genotyping EXTRA II assay (Fujirebio, Japan).

2.4. LAMP amplification

The final LAMP reaction mix contained DNA sample from either cell lines or clinical samples (in most experiments using the final amount of 150 ng), 1 × Master Mix from the WarmStart LAMP Kit, set of primers (final concentration of 0.2 μ M outer primers F3/B3 and 1.6 μ M inner primers FIP/BIP), and 0.035 mM bio-dUTP. LAMP reaction was performed at 66 °C for 40 min, followed by polymerase inactivation at 80 °C for 5 min. LAMP products were visualized on 1.5% agarose gel in TBE buffer with GelRed Nucleic Acid Gel Stain (Biotium, USA).

2.5. Preparation of DNA biosensor layers

Each layer was prepared by casting a drop of the mixture to fully cover the working electrode (~5 μ L, freshly prepared on daily basis), avoiding application into counter and pseudoreference electrodes surrounding the working electrode. As a first layer, we applied the mixture of 10 μ M thiolated CP and 2 mM of MCH, prepared in immobilization buffer (IB, 10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, 0.3 M NaCl, pH 8.0), and incubated it for 2 h at room temperature (RT). After that, the electrodes were rinsed with deionized water, dried with argon, and incubated with

0.1% BSA solution (prepared in IB) for 30 min at RT. Thereafter, the electrodes were rinsed and dried again, and incubated with LAMP products for another 30 min at RT. Afterwards, we applied SPP (diluted 1:500 in casein blocking buffer) and incubated for final 30 min at RT. Finally, the electrodes were thoroughly rinsed and dried, ready for subsequent EC measurements.

2.6. Electrochemical measurements

The eight-electrode AuSPE chips modified with the above-mentioned layers were inserted into a DropSens interface (Metrohm DropSens, CAST8X) to connect with the multipotentiostat. Then, 50 μl of TMB solution, serving as a substrate for the streptavidin-horseradish peroxidase conjugate (SPP), was dropped to cover all three electrodes, i.e., working, counter and pseudoreference electrode, followed by an amperometry measurement at -0.2 V to monitor the electric current from the enzymatic reaction for 120 s.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was measured in 5 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ (1:1) in 0.1 M KCl solution, with the scan rate of 100 mV/s.

2.7. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Samples on the AuSPEs were directly examined by SEM (Vega, Tescan Orsay Holding, Brno). SEM micrographs were obtained using

secondary electron detection (SE) at a voltage of 15 kV using 5000 times magnification.

2.8. Statistical analysis

Kappa value calculations were performed by QuickCalcs online statistical tool (<https://www.graphpad.com/quickcalcs/kappa1/>). All other statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism software (version 7.03). Sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values were calculated using a Chi-square test by comparing EC data with PCR results, and the significance (p -value) of these results was calculated with Fisher's exact test. Mann-Whitney test was used to calculate the significance between electrochemical measurements of positive and negative clinical samples.

3. Results

3.1. Assay overview

The principle of our assay is depicted in Fig. 1. Briefly, DNA from crude biological samples, i.e., either cancer cells or cervical smears collected by gynecologist, was first extracted as described above. If the extracted DNA sample contained HPV DNA of interest (HPV16 or HPV18), it became amplified with the LAMP reaction using HPV16- or

Fig. 1. Simplified workflow of proposed bioassay. (A) Gold electrode was first modified with the thiolated capture probe (thiolated CP) and mercaptohexanol (MCH), followed by an incubation with the BSA. Afterwards, (B) thiolated CPs hybridized with the corresponding HPV16/18 LAMP amplicons containing biotinylated nucleobases (biotin-dUTPs), which in the next step interacted with (C) streptavidin-peroxidase polymer (SPP). (D) Finally, TMB substrate that was oxidized by HRP was electrochemically reduced and monitored via amperometry. (E) Redox reactions occurring at the electrode surface between SPP, TMB and H_2O_2 . (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

HPV18-specific primers. The LAMP reaction was conducted separately for HPV16 and for HPV18. DNA sample was usually divided into two tubes; primers for HPV16 were in the first tube to check for presence of the HPV16, and primers for HPV18 were in the second tube. We have previously tested various different primer sets from both *E6* and *E7* regions (Anton et al., 2020; Bartosik et al., 2018; Izadi et al., 2021), but the best results were obtained with the primer sets shown in Table S1. We targeted a more variable *E6/E7* region of the HPV genome, making it easier to discriminate between the types; in the case of HPV16, we used the *E6* region of the viral genome, while for HPV18, we used the *E7* region. Due to addition of bio-dUTP into the LAMP reaction, the LAMP products were internally labeled with biotin.

Commercial disposable gold electrode chips with eight working electrodes were first modified with the mixture of a thiolated capture probe (CP) and a MCH. CP was either complementary for HPV16 (CP_HP16) or HPV18 (CP_HP18) region of the target DNA that was amplified with the LAMP reaction. MCH was a blocking agent to suppress non-specific adsorption as well as a diluent that helped CP to adopt upright conformation for easier hybridization with LAMP products. To further block remaining unoccupied sites and to prevent cross-reactivity of HPV16/18 LAMP products, we also employed BSA solution in the next step (see 3.3. for more details). After these blocking steps, LAMP products were introduced to the gold surface to bind with the corresponding CPs. It was reported that LAMP reaction yields amplicons belonging into four different structural categories: single loop amplicons, terminated amplicons, single stranded amplicons and partially double stranded amplicons (Kaur et al., 2020). Since we did not use any thermal denaturation to facilitate CP binding to the double-stranded amplicons, we assume that only single-stranded amplicons are detectable with our electrochemical assay. Next, SPP was added, binding to the biotin in the LAMP product after successful hybridization. Finally, TMB solution served as a substrate for EC measurement of the activity of a peroxidase; enzymatically oxidized TMB was reduced at the gold electrode surface back to TMB, and the resulting electric current was monitored by amperometry.

3.2. Characterization of the biosensor

We characterized the surface of the gold electrode after each incubation step by SEM and cyclic voltammetry. Fig. S1 shows SEM images of bare AuSPE prior to any modification (bare electrode), and after each incubation step. We used the SE detection mode that is more suitable for biological applications and surface and near-surface characterizations, using 5000 × magnification. Modification of the surface with CP + MCH (Figure S1.2) or BSA (Figure S1.3) yielded similar SEM images as the bare electrode (Figure S1.1), perhaps due to a low magnification factor (higher magnification did not result in more information, but only in more blurred images). Cubic structures apparent in Figure S1.2 and S1.3 are most probably crystals of the salt present in the immobilization buffer. Changes in SEM images became more apparent once the electrode surface was covered with the LAMP product of a significant size (Figure S1.4A). This is a common feature of the LAMP reaction that it produces amplicons ranging from several hundred up to several thousand base pairs long, forming so-called cauliflower structures (Kaur et al., 2020). The most apparent change, however, was obtained with the addition of SPP, composed of activated streptavidin and horseradish peroxidase molecules covalently conjugated to a polymer backbone; the Figure S1.5 shows leaf-like structures of this polymer that is sufficiently large to be observed at this magnification. We also compared surfaces with (Figure S1.4A) and without the LAMP product (Figure S1.4B, blank) to see that the structures originate from the amplified DNA product and not from the components of the LAMP master mix.

Then, we examined the blocking effects of individual layers by CV using $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ as a redox probe. As shown in Fig. S2, after modifying the gold surface we observed a decrease in the anodic and cathodic peak currents when compared with the voltammetric behavior

of bare Au surfaces. This decrease was most pronounced when applying final layer of SPP; previous layers caused only slight decrease, which can probably be explained either by a short co-adsorption time for the first CP + MCH layer (2 h instead of more commonly used overnight adsorption), leading to a less dense layer, or by a larger dilution of BSA (using only 0.1% solution). Since these conditions were shown to be most suitable for amperometry, we kept them also during CV experiments. Results from both techniques suggested that the formation of individual layers was successful.

3.3. Optimization studies

We tested two different variations of electrode surface modification with DNA capture probe, i.e., (a) more common approach with overnight CP incubation at 4 °C, followed by MCH incubation at RT for 1 h, and (b) short co-adsorption of the mixture of CP with MCH for 2 h at RT to significantly decrease overall time of the protocol. Interestingly, the results did not vary that much, yielding similar signals and noises for both approaches (Fig. S3A), and we thus selected a shorter co-adsorption approach in subsequent studies.

It is widely accepted that the MCH blocking suppresses nonspecific binding of undesired molecules (Campuzano et al., 2011; Ferrario et al., 2013; Tichoniuk et al., 2010; Xu et al., 2019). However, we observed false positive signals when applying HPV18 LAMP products on the gold electrode modified with the capture probe for HPV16 (CP_HP16), and vice versa (see Fig. 2). This cross-reactivity issue could arise due to a nonspecific binding of the LAMP-amplified DNA or SPP conjugates to the gold surface. If the nonspecific binding was due to the SPP, this would translate into high background noise in blank samples without BSA step (see Fig. 2, grey bars). Using HPV16 primers, however, we obtained only slightly higher signals for blank samples without BSA step as compared to blanks with BSA step (Fig. 2), indicating that only minor nonspecific HRP binding may have occurred. No differences were obtained for HPV18 primers. On the other hand, previous studies by Herne and Tarlov showed nonspecific binding of single-stranded DNA molecules to flat gold surfaces, presumably by means of interactions provided by the exposed bases (Herne and Tarlov 1997). Later, Sandstrom et al. described this behavior also for double-stranded DNA interacting with gold nanoparticles, which they explained as an ion-induced dipole interaction whereby the charges of the phosphate groups of DNA induced a dipole in the highly polarizable gold particles (Sandstrom et al., 2003). Moreover, they also discussed that the amount of nonspecific binding to the gold was lower compared to the DNA oligos designed to attach specifically by SH group; in other words, thiolated CPs bind preferentially via SH groups while LAMP products that do not contain SH groups bind nonspecifically. Because the cross-reactivity issue appeared after 2 h co-adsorption of CP and MCH, we wondered whether overnight adsorption of thiolated CP followed by 1 h adsorption of MCH will resolve this issue. Although chemisorption is quite fast, self-assembled monolayers (SAM) are dynamic and to optimize the reproducibility of the SAM and minimize their defects, a reorganization process taking several hours is usually recommended (Love et al., 2005). However, the cross-reactivity issue remained even after the overnight adsorption (Fig. S3B), suggesting that the LAMP products may non-specifically bind even to an organized SAM. We then tried various other alternatives to resolve this issue, such as the application of various third thiolated components (hexanedithiol or DTT), or addition of an extra blocking step with either casein or BSA to suppress false positives as much as possible. The cross-reactivity issues remained after employing hexanedithiol or DTT (not shown), and only slight improvement was seen when using casein blocking buffer. The best suppression was obtained with 0.1% BSA solution (applied for 30 min at RT after CP incubation step), which significantly reduced false positive EC signals from noncomplementary LAMP amplicons (Fig. 2) yet kept the positive signals from complementary LAMP products at a sufficiently high level.

Fig. 2. Cross-reactivity experiment. CP for HPV16 (top) and HPV18 (bottom) were incubated with both LAMP-amplified CaSki DNA and HeLa DNA. Without BSA blocking step (grey bars), noncomplementary amplified DNA bound nonspecifically and yielded EC signals. With BSA blocking step (black bars), this nonspecific behavior was suppressed. Error bars are from duplicate measurements.

We show in Fig. 3 that EC detection of HeLa LAMP products indeed requires all assay steps, i.e., hybridization with CP, addition of SPP as well as its substrate TMB. A negative control experiment without DNA

Fig. 3. Comparison of EC signals for HeLa HPV DNA having either all steps included (ALL), or without addition of HeLa DNA (no template control, NTC), capture probe (-Probe), mercaptohexanol (-MCH), BSA (-BSA), streptavidin-polymer peroxidase (-SPP) and TMB substrate (-TMB).

target is shown as well. All these control experiments led to negligible EC signals. Note that when applying BSA blocking step, elimination of the CP leads to a small signal. This is important since it indicates that LAMP product does not bind nonspecifically to the electrode but indeed is hybridized to the CP. As expected, MCH and BSA elimination did not cause EC signal drop; these molecules are important to block non-specific adsorptions, but the assay generates positive signals also without them. In fact, EC currents were higher when omitting MCH or BSA, but on the other hand, the cross-reactivity issues described above became substantial without these components. The cross-reactivity issue is often inadequately addressed in papers where amplification products are hybridized with thiolated CP at the gold electrode, and we highly encourage other authors to always check whether the surface is blocked enough to prevent non-specific binding of noncomplementary sequences.

We also compared two different peroxidase substrates, i.e., TMB and hydroquinone (not shown). Although the hydroquinone performed better in our previously published assays using carbon electrodes (Bartosik et al. 2016, 2018), in current assay the TMB outperformed hydroquinone in terms of signal-to-noise ratio, suggesting that the electrode surface might play an important role in a choice of the substrate. Moreover, TMB as a ready-to-use solution is less toxic than hydroquinone. All additional optimized parameters are shown in Table 1, where we give a list of tested values/conditions in one column and the selected one in another column.

3.4. Analytical characteristics

Fig. 4A shows EC values from different cancer cell lines, i.e., cervical cancer cell lines positive for HPV16 (CaSki and SiHa) and for HPV18 (HeLa and C4-I), as well as non-cervical cancer cell lines negative for HPVs, MCF-7 and HT-29. It is apparent that LAMP reaction with HPV16 primers proceeded successfully only on CaSki and SiHa DNA that both contain HPV16, while all remaining DNA samples from other cell lines were negative, reaching the level of a blank measurement. Similarly, LAMP reaction with HPV18 primers successfully amplified only DNA from HeLa and C4-I DNA (both containing HPV18 DNA), while other samples were negative. Our primers and probes are thus selective enough for the given HPV strain; moreover, this selectivity was further confirmed by the cross-reactivity measurements shown in Fig. 2.

The LAMP as an exponential amplification technique provides good sensitivity, comparable to that of PCR (Bartosik et al., 2018). In our work, we tested the detection limit of our assay by decreasing the amount of HeLa or CaSki DNA into the LAMP mixture. In both cases, we tested the range between 10 pg and 150 ng of genomic DNA and observed levelling of the signal above 5 ng for HeLa DNA (Fig. 4B) and above 1 ng for CaSki DNA (Fig. S4). Considering the standard deviation of individual data points, we were able to reliably discriminate as little as 50 pg of HeLa DNA and as little as 100 pg of CaSki DNA. Below, we

Table 1

List of tested parameters and conditions along with the selected ones.

Parameter	Tested	Selected
LAMP reaction time	10–90 min	40 min ^a
LAMP reaction DNA input	0–500 ng	150 ng
CP concentration	0.1–10 µM	10 µM
MCH concentration	0.1–10 mM	2 mM
BSA amount	1%, 0.1%, 0.01%	0.1%
blocking agents	HDT ^b , DTT ^c , CBB ^d , BSA	BSA
co-adsorption time	15–120 min	120 min
SPP incubation time	15–60 min	30 min

^a Applies for majority of experiments, except for determining limit of detection where we used 90 min LAMP reaction time to improve sensitivity.

^b HDT - hexanedithiol.

^c DTT - dithiothreitol.

^d CBB - casein blocking buffer.

Fig. 4. (A) Selectivity experiment. Current values for different cancer cell lines, using primers and probes for HPV16 (black) and for HPV18 (grey). CaSki and SiHa cell lines are positive for HPV16, HeLa and C4-I are positive for HPV18, other cell lines are HPV-negative. (B) Dependence of electric current on HeLa DNA input into the LAMP reaction (using HPV18 primers and probe). Time of LAMP reaction was 90 min to increase sensitivity. Inset: zoomed section of the main graph, showing low values in part of graph corresponding to picograms of DNA used as a template. Error bars are from duplicate measurements.

show that this detection limit is enough to determine a presence of a viral DNA in routinely collected clinical samples from patients (women with suspected cervical precancerous lesions).

3.5. Clinical samples analysis

To evaluate applicability of our biosensor in clinical settings, we selected fifteen clinical samples with and without HPV16 or HPV18 infection, at different stages of a disease. Age range of patients was 26–61 years. All samples were originally identified with INNO-LiPA assay (Fujirebio, Japan) in a clinical laboratory. Twelve of fifteen samples were HPV-positive (harboring various HPV types) and three were HPV-negative; more specifically, three were HPV16-positive, three were HPV18-positive, three had HPV16/18 co-infections, and six were HPV16/18 negative. Regarding the disease stage, one cervical sample tissue was considered as healthy, two tissue samples were characterized as LSILs (low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions), and twelve tissue samples were HSILs (two of which progressed into carcinoma *in situ*).

After DNA extraction and LAMP amplification using HPV16/18 primers, DNA samples were hybridized with the corresponding capture probe at the biosensor surface that was previously blocked with MCH and BSA to minimize non-specific adsorption and cross-reactivity. EC

data for all fifteen clinical samples, tested for both HPV16 and HPV18 infection, are shown in Fig. 5B, E. The threshold value above which we considered sample to be positive was set empirically to 1.0 µA, which was about four times higher than a median of a blank measurement (Table S2). We compare EC data with a standard technique, i.e., agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR products (Fig. 5A, D); this direct comparison shows one mismatched sample for HPV16 detection (i.e., the sample where our EC data and the gel do not correlate; here sample #6) and one mismatched sample in HPV18 detection (sample #11), while remaining samples show good correlation between these two techniques. Original gel images, including β-actin as a DNA input control, are shown in Fig. S5.

Furthermore, the EC data for both HPV16 and HPV18 are presented as scatter plots in Fig. 5C, F. The dots represent the mean current values for each clinical sample (calculated from duplicates). Dots are grouped into two categories based on results from electrochemistry: HPV16-negative (left) and HPV16-positive (right) samples (same for HPV18). In each category, we show an overall mean value together with SD from all samples of that category. According to the Mann-Whitney test, EC results show statistically highly significant differences between HPV16-negative controls and HPV16-positive women (p -value < 0.001) as well as between HPV18-negative controls and HPV18-positive women (p -value < 0.001). More details on EC data for both positive and negative patient samples as well as for blank measurements (medians, mean values, SD values etc.) can be found in Table S2.

To evaluate performance of our assay, we compared it to the PCR as a gold standard. For HPV16, the sensitivity of our assay was 85.71% (percentage of infected individuals that were correctly identified as having the condition), specificity was 100% (percentage of healthy individuals that were correctly identified as not having the condition), positive predictive value was 100% (PPV, a probability that the subject with a positive result is truly infected) and negative predictive value was 88.89% (NPV, a probability that the subject with negative result does not have an infection). The Kappa value, which quantifies an agreement between two methods, was 0.865, corresponding to almost perfect agreement. The number of observed agreements were 14 out of 15 (93.33%). For HPV18, we observed sensitivity of 100%, specificity of 90%, PPV of 83.33%, NPV of 100% and kappa value of 0.857, corresponding to almost perfect agreement. The number of observed agreements were also 14 out of 15 (93.33%). These data are summarized also in Table S3. Interestingly, studies by other authors showed different sensitivities and specificities when comparing LAMP and PCR (Baba et al., 2021; Goodarzi et al., 2017), which could explain the two discrepancies observed in our assay. The region amplified by PCR lies within the region amplified by LAMP (but LAMP primers cover longer sequence, approx. 250 bp, compared to 100 bp for PCR). Since LAMP uses four primers instead of two, high sequence homology between HPV strains may lead to false positives in PCR while no amplification occurs in LAMP, which was shown to be more specific. On the other hand, PCR was shown to be more sensitive (Baba et al., 2021).

Finally, we compared both our data, i.e., from LAMP reaction with subsequent EC measurement and from PCR with gel electrophoresis, with the commercially available INNO-LiPA HPV genotyping assay used for clinical analysis in hospitals (Table S4). Since our gel electrophoresis visualization perfectly correlated with the data from INNO-LiPA (they match in 100% cases because both methods use PCR reaction), the statistics when comparing our EC data with the INNO-LiPA is the same as shown above for the gel electrophoresis. This indicates that our assay, which does not require PCR amplification, has very good capabilities to distinguish HPV-positive and HPV-negative women already in precancerous stages.

4. Conclusions

Our data suggest a good capability of the developed biosensor to detect DNA from the two most common oncogenic HPV types, HPV16

Fig. 5. Analysis of clinical material. Top: Agarose gels showing PCR products from clinical samples used in the study. Primers for PCR reaction: (A) HPV16 and (D) HPV18. Middle: Bar graph shows current values of fifteen clinical samples with various HPV status, using primers and a probe for (B) HPV16 and (E) HPV18. Based on PCR, samples 1–3 were HPV16-positive, samples 4–9 were negative for HPV16 or HPV18, samples 10–12 had co-infection for both HPV16 and HPV18, and samples 13–15 were HPV18-positive. Cell lines are shown as positive controls (CaSki for HPV16 and HeLa for HPV18), blank is a non-template control. Dashed line represents a cut-off value above which we considered the sample to be positive. Error bars are from duplicate measurements. Bottom: Scatter plots showing mean EC values of HPV 16-negative and HPV 16-positive clinical samples using (C) HPV 16 and (F) HPV18 primers and probes.

and HPV18. The biosensor is highly specific due to a LAMP reaction that uses four primers to amplify both sequences, and due to an application of a capture probe immobilized at the AuSPE. In this work, we omitted a use of magnetic beads that undoubtedly possess many advantages for separation of biomolecules (Palecek and Fojta 2007), but also make the overall protocol more complex due to longer washing steps. Instead, we used very popular AuSPEs that can be easily modified and quickly washed. By using eight-electrode chips, where eight measurements can be carried out simultaneously, we greatly decreased measurement times.

Initially, we struggled with the cross-reactivity when the LAMP products that were not complementary to the capture probe were nonspecifically adsorbed at the electrode surface. We needed to include an extra blocking step using BSA solution, which, however, also decreased EC current in positive control experiments. Nevertheless, this decrease was not detrimental as we were able to detect picogram amounts of DNA from cancer cells. Furthermore, we significantly decreased a time required for chemisorption of a thiolated CP (from common overnight adsorption to only 2 h) without significantly compromising the signal intensity, which was also demonstrated in few other studies (Florea et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2009). Importantly, this simple design devoid of nanomaterials or complex layers was still sufficiently sensitive to determine HPV infection in precancerous tissue samples. We are aware that this study used only fifteen clinical samples, demonstrating only a proof-of-concept, and more samples would be needed to verify it in clinical settings. However, we believe that the combination of LAMP reaction and electrochemistry can be potentially useful not only in early diagnostics of cervical cancer,

but also for the detection of other DNA or RNA-based cancer biomarkers.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ravery Sebuyoya: Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Ludmila Moranova:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Nasim Izadi:** Methodology, Validation. **Lukas Moran:** Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Roman Hrstka:** Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing. **Milan Anton:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing. **Martin Bartosik:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by Czech Health Research Council (project no. NU21-08-00057), by the project National Institute for Cancer Research (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5102) - Funded by the European Union - Next Generation EU, by the European Regional Development Fund (project BBMRI-CZ.: Biobank network – a versatile platform for the research of the etiopathogenesis of diseases,

reg. no. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_013/0001674), by the project BBMRI-CZ no. LM2018125, MH CZ - DRO (MMCI, 00209805) and by Masaryk University (MUNI/A/1398/2021).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosx.2022.100224>.

References

- Anton, M., Moranova, L., Hrstka, R., Bartosik, M., 2020. *Anal. Methods* 12 (6), 822–829.
- Baba, M.M., Bitew, M., Fokam, J., Lelo, E.A., Ahidjo, A., Asmamaw, K., Beloumou, G.A., Bulimo, W.D., Buratti, E., Chenwi, C., Dadi, H., D'Agaro, P., De Conti, L., Fainguem, N., Gadzama, G., Maiuri, P., Majanja, J., Meshack, W., Ndjolo, A., Nkenfou, C., Oderinde, B.S., Opanda, S.M., Segat, L., Stuani, C., Symekher, S.L., Takou, D., Tesfaye, K., Triolo, G., Tuki, K., Zacchigna, S., Marcello, A., 2021. *eClinicalMedicine* 40, 101101.
- Bartosik, M., Durikova, H., Vojtesek, B., Anton, M., Jandakova, E., Hrstka, R., 2016. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 83, 300–305.
- Bartosik, M., Jirakova, L., 2019. *Curr. Opin. Electrochem.* 14, 96–103.
- Bartosik, M., Jirakova, L., Anton, M., Vojtesek, B., Hrstka, R., 2018. *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1042, 37–43.
- Campuzano, S., Kuralay, F., Lobo-Castanon, M.J., Bartosik, M., Vyavahare, K., Palecek, E., Haake, D.A., Wang, J., 2011. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 26 (8), 3577–3583.
- Campuzano, S., Yanez-Sedeno, P., Pingarron, J.M., 2017a. *Chemelectrochem* 4 (4), 753–777.
- Campuzano, S., Yanez-Sedeno, P., Pingarron, J.M., 2017b. *Sensors* 17 (4).
- Dunne, E.F., Park, I.U., 2013. *Infect. Dis. Clin.* 27 (4), 765–+.
- Ferapontova, E.E., 2017. *Curr. Opin. Electrochem.* 5 (1), 218–225.
- Ferrario, A., Scaramuzza, M., Pasqualotto, E., De Toni, A., Paccagnella, A., 2013. *J. Electroanal. Chem.* 689, 57–62.
- Florea, A., Taleat, Z., Cristea, C., Mazloum-Ardakani, M., Săndulescu, R., 2013. *Electrochem. Commun.* 33, 127–130.
- Goodarzi, M., Shahhosseiny, M.H., Bayat, M., Hashemi, S.J., Ghahri, M., 2017. *Microbiol. Res.* 8 (2).
- Herne, T.M., Tarlov, M.J., 1997. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 119 (38), 8916–8920.
- Islam, M.N., Gopalan, V., Haque, M.H., Masud, Mostafa K., Hossain, M.S.A., Yamauchi, Y., Nguyen, N.-T., Lam, A.K.-Y., Shiddiky, M.J.A., 2017. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 98, 227–233.
- Izadi, N., Sebuyoya, R., Moranova, L., Hrstka, R., Anton, M., Bartosik, M., 2021. *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1187, 339145.
- Kaur, N., Thota, N., Toley, B.J., 2020. *Comput. Struct. Biotechnol. J.* 18, 2336–2346.
- Kilic, T., Erdem, A., Ozsoz, M., Carrara, S., 2018. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 99, 525–546.
- Liu, P., Liu, M., Yin, H., Zhou, Y., Ai, S., 2015. *Sens. Actuators B Chem.* 220, 101–106.
- Love, J.C., Estroff, L.A., Kriebel, J.K., Nuzzo, R.G., Whitesides, G.M., 2005. *Chem. Rev.* 105 (4), 1103–1170.
- Mandler, D., Kraus-Ophir, S., 2011. *J. Solid State Electrochem.* 15 (7–8), 1535–1558.
- Martens, J.W.M., Margossian, A.L., Schmitt, M., Foekens, J., Harbeck, N., 2009. *Future Oncol.* 5 (8), 1245–1256.
- Mikeska, T., Bock, C., Do, H., Dobrovic, A., 2012. *Expert Rev. Mol. Diagn.* 12 (5), 473–487.
- Mincu, N.-B., Lazar, V., Stan, D., Mihailescu, C.M., Iosub, R., Mateescu, A.L., 2020. *Diagnostics* 10 (8), 517.
- Miranda-Castro, R., de-Los-Santos-Alvarez, N., Lobo-Castanon, M.J., 2019. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 411 (19), 4265–4275.
- Morris, B.J., 2005. *Clin. Chem. Lab. Med.* 43 (11), 1171–1177.
- Nabok, A., Abu-Ali, H., Takita, S., Smith, D.P., 2021. *Chemosensors* 9 (4), 59.
- Osazuwa-Peters, N., Boakye, E.A., Mohammed, K.A., Tobo, B.B., Geneus, C.J., Schootman, M., 2017. *Prev. Med.* 99, 299–304.
- Palecek, E., Fojta, M., 2007. *Talanta* 74 (3), 276–290.
- Pessoa, L.S., Heringer, M., Ferrer, V.P., 2020. *Crit. Rev. Oncol./Hematol.* 155.
- Sandstrom, P., Boncheva, M., Akerman, B., 2003. *Langmuir* 19 (18), 7537–7543.
- Schiffman, M., Castle, P.E., Jeronimo, J., Rodriguez, A.C., Wacholder, S., 2007. *Lancet* 370 (9590), 890–907.
- Sommerova, L., Anton, M., Bouchalova, P., Jasickova, H., Rak, V., Jandakova, E., Selingerova, I., Bartosik, M., Vojtesek, B., Hrstka, R., 2019. *Antivir. Res.* 163, 185–192.
- Steenbergen, R.D., Snijders, P.J., Heideman, D.A., Meijer, C.J., 2014. *Nat. Rev. Cancer* 14 (6), 395–405.
- Tichoniuk, M., Gwiazdowska, D., Ligaj, M., Filipiak, M., 2010. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 26 (4), 1618–1623.
- Voccia, D., Sosnowska, M., Bettazzi, F., Roscigno, G., Fratini, E., De Francis, V., Condorelli, G., Chitta, R., D'Souza, F., Kutner, W., Palchetti, I., 2017. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 87, 1012–1019.
- Wittmann, J., Jack, H.M., 2010. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta-Rev. Cancer* 1806 (2), 200–207.
- Wu, J., Campuzano, S., Halford, C., Haake, D.A., Wang, J., 2010. *Anal. Chem.* 82 (21), 8830–8837.
- Xi, X., Li, T., Huang, Y., Sun, J., Zhu, Y., Yang, Y., Lu, Z.J., 2017. *Noncoding RNA* 3 (1).
- Xu, X.X., Makaraviciute, A., Kumar, S., Wen, C.Y., Sjodin, M., Abdurakhmanov, E., Danielson, U.H., Nyholm, L., Zhang, Z., 2019. *Anal. Chem.* 91 (22), 14697–14704.
- Yang, W., Gerasimov, J.Y., Lai, R.Y., 2009. *ChemComm* (20), 2902–2904.